

COUNCIL ON LIBRARY RESOURCES

One Dupont Circle • Washington, D. C. • 20036

Tel. 202-296-4757

REPORT TO

THE FORD FOUNDATION

July 1, 1977 - June 30, 1978

Grant Number 560-0219D&E

Council On Library Resources, Inc.

THE YEAR 1977-1978

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FOREWORD

An annual report is by definition a look backwards in time - something the Council on Library Resources has been able to do with a sense of accomplishment since 1956. Reflection is especially rewarding this year because we consider not only 1977-78 but by extension the decade of Fred Cole's presidency of CLR. The substance of this report is in large part an addition to his record and a further testimonial to his sensitivity for the concerns and interests of individuals and the complex nature of the events that together mold library service and shape library history.

There is no intent to repeat here that which was thoroughly recorded in the 20th Annual Report of the Council and supplemented last year. The review of activities during the year that ended June 30, 1978, underscores a continuity of interest that has marked CLR itself. At the same time it suggests that some specific aspects of our work have come to an end or are nearing completion.

While CLR goals reflect the judgments of its directors and president, progress actually made is traced to the contributions of many individuals. Two are due specific mention. In the considerable effort to bring the promise of computing technology to bear on library operations, no one has been more prominent than Lawrence G. Livingston. Larry's death in midyear created a gap that will take many to fill. Essentially the same statement can be made about Edith Lesser who retired as the year closed from her dual posts as assistant to the president and secretary-treasurer of the Council. Edith was centrally involved in all CLR operations and gave much substance to the entire enterprise.

In terms of people and programs, the year 1978 really was one for the record. An era ends by looking at that record and another begins with speculation about the future and the hope that at some distant point in time the process of reflection will be as interesting and as rewarding as it is today.

Warren J. Haas
President

ON THE NATIONAL SCALE

The current inflationary decade has been a difficult one for American academic and research libraries. Successive years of rising costs, changing patterns of enrollments, and budgets reduced in purchasing power have forced a reconsideration of priorities for most and often severe retrenchment. Although Library Journal reported in its 1977 news roundup an upsurge in state and local funding, the passage of Proposition 13 in California following on the heels of a severe winter energy crisis were reminders that many problems remain unsolved. For many librarians the key to survival in the tough years ahead appears to be collective action and an increased sharing of resources -- the development, according to one university librarian, of "shared dependencies."

A substantial portion of the Council's work during the 1970s has involved various pieces of what might be the apex of current collective efforts, a national library and information system. Such a coordinated system, the primary goal of which would be to improve access to information for all sectors of society, would

facilitate the sharing of resources and eliminate wasteful duplication. In 1977 the Council embarked on a project to design what may become an important node in a national system: a national periodicals center.

Planning for a National Periodicals Center

Last November the Library of Congress asked the Council to prepare a technical development plan for a U.S. national periodicals center (NPC). The need for such a facility was formalized by the National Commission on Libraries and Information Science (NCLIS) in its 1977 document Effective Access to Periodical Literature, which recommended that the Library of Congress (LC) assume responsibility for developing, managing, and operating the center. LC and the Council agreed that the plan would be put together in such a way that it could be used by the Library or any other agency prepared to assume responsibility for the center's creation. Several foundations contributed to the cost of preparing the document, which, as this report year ends, is substantially completed and is scheduled for publication in August 1978 under the title "A National Periodicals Center Technical Development Plan."

The Council's planning team is composed of CLR and LC staff under the leadership of C. Lee Jones, health sciences librarian at Columbia University. The plan contains the technical requirements for services, collection, management, personnel, equipment, data processing support systems, prices, costs, and location and design of a facility. Implementation and a possible governance structure also are discussed. Throughout the planning effort, the center's primary goal has been kept firmly in mind: to improve access to periodical literature for libraries and thus to individuals using libraries.

After an initial phasing-in period, all libraries, networks, and consortia would have access to the NPC. A pricing schedule has been proposed that varies according to the age, frequency of request, and copyright status of the periodical article requested. All transactions would require payment of a processing fee estimated to be in the range of \$3.00 to 3.50. If required, copyright or sales fees would be added. In any case, librarians using the NPC would be assured that for any item received from the center, the appropriate fees would have been paid. At the same time premiums on items that are heavily requested should encourage the development and enhancement of local resources for this category of material.

The plan further proposes a new relationship between a national periodicals center and the publishing community. Specifically, the plan states that the NPC will not operate in a way that would jeopardize the legitimate rights of publishers to the economic benefits of their publishing effort. Instead it is proposed that the center become a service and fulfillment outlet -- a retail sales agent -- for at least some publishers. For example, the NPC might provide a back-issue service (probably in microform) or an article sales service for as long as the article remained protected by copyright. The NPC might become an outlet for on-demand publishing and/or a source for the full text of material published in synoptic form. While this sort of relationship might tend to modify traditional information production or distribution functions, it is hoped that the service would generate some income for publishers while improving access to the periodical literature that library users need. The emphasis throughout the plan is on meeting the needs of libraries and their patrons.

It is projected that the national periodicals center will contain a collection of 36,000 periodicals initially, then grow through the addition of titles and backfiles to the point at which it might include more than 60,000 current titles. All

subjects would be included except clinical medicine, access to which is provided by the Regional Medical Library Program of the National Library of Medicine. A finding tool would be published that would list all of the titles available either from the center itself or from referral libraries with which the NPC would have contracted to provide access to specific titles. Although much of the collection would be stored in microform, the medium of fulfillment would be paper photocopy, unless microform were requested. The orders would be sent via first-class mail for the most part. The plan projects that 90 percent of all valid requests would be filled within a 24-hour or one-working-day cycle.

To pull together the resources necessary for establishing the NPC and to ensure close coordination between NPC operation and the development of other national programs (e.g. bibliographic control, communications, preservation, etc.), the plan calls for a "new, imaginative" approach to the governance of the facility.

A two-tier structure at the national level is proposed. The first tier would consist of a new organization with authority and funds to establish and coordinate such programs as those mentioned above that are best handled at the national level. The second tier would consist of the separate governing bodies of those programs, each of which would be responsible to the first tier. If such a coordinating agency were created, its first operating responsibility would be to establish a national periodicals center.

If an NPC were established what would be its effect on the world of libraries and their users? Of primary importance, of course, would be the enhanced capability of libraries to provide their users promptly and at a reasonable cost with copies of articles from a wide range of popular and obscure journals. Libraries would be able to make rational decisions based on discrete cost data about what periodicals should be maintained in

their collections, with the utmost assurance that a known body of literature was readily available and would be preserved. Discrete data on frequency of use of individual titles would be available, and collections could thus be shaped to meet the actual needs of local users. The burden of net lending should ease from the large institutions, and all libraries should discover that the aggregate costs of interlibrary loan of periodicals are lessening.

Thus, "A National Periodicals Center Technical Development Plan" goes beyond the technical design of a periodicals facility. It advocates a new equation, one that involves authors and publishers and protects their rights while simultaneously increasing the availability of their products to all. Indeed, the plan views the NPC as providing new options in the distribution and inventory of periodical literature with benefits for those who publish, those who store and retrieve, and ultimately, those who use periodical literature. Society has much to gain from the development of an efficient, reliable, and responsive document delivery system for periodical material.

Promoting Use of the ISSN

Not the least of the NPC's effects envisaged by librarians would be an improvement in the bibliographic control of serial literature. Of all the parts of a library's collection, the identification and control of serials is the most troublesome. The problem is partially generic: while books have single, usually unique titles, periodicals frequently have similar titles and are identified by individual libraries in a variety of ways. Although a succession of standards for the identification of serials has been developed over the years, libraries as a group have failed to apply any of them consistently. Identifying a title precisely, particularly without an issue in hand, often becomes a guessing game.

In the plan for a national periodicals center, the team proposed that the center use the International Serials Data System (ISDS). The ISDS is an international network of operational centers jointly responsible for the creation and maintenance of computer-based data banks that contain essential information for the identification of serials. The aim of the ISDS is to provide a reliable registry of the world's serial publications. Its most attractive feature is its responsibility for assigning to each serial a unique identification number, the International Standard Serial Number (ISSN). Consistent application by a national periodicals center of this standard, it is thought, will tend to promote its use by libraries nationwide.

In April 1978 the Council made a grant to the Library of Congress to support a set of activities that should further encourage the use of the ISSN. The United States Postal Service (USPS) has agreed to use the ISSN as the official registration number for certain serials mailed at second-class rates and will require that it be printed on the serial. LC's National Serials Data Program, the United States National Center of the ISDS, will work closely with the Postal Service to provide assignments of numbers for appropriate publications. The Council's grant will be used to engage the services of Cornell University, Harvard University, and MINITEX (Minnesota Interlibrary Telecommunications Exchange) to help identify those serials for which ISSN are appropriate. Registration of those titles, estimated to number 13,000, will be accomplished by October 1, 1978.

Committee for the Coordination of National Bibliographic Control

Improved identification and recording of periodicals would constitute major progress toward a coherent system of national bibliographic control. To achieve such a system covering all publications requires a cooperative effort to record all items published in the United States in terms of their intellectual content and physical properties and to merge those records into a national bibliographic data base or bases. The data would then be shared by all the various nodes that make up the national library and information system in whatever way their users require.

In April 1974 45 members of the library, abstracting and indexing, publishing, information dissemination, and allied communities met to design programs of action that would lay the foundation for an improved national bibliographic system. Out of that meeting grew the Committee for the Coordination of National Bibliographic Control (CCNBC) whose members were charged with such tasks as developing national strategies, identifying areas for standardization, protecting systems integrity, providing national direction for international participation, and assigning responsibility to accomplish specific tasks.

Jointly sponsored by the Council, the National Science Foundation (NSF), and NCLIS, CCNBC members meet four times a year. Major concerns during the past year have been the commissioning of a study on standardized message text formats for efficient communications in a bibliographic network environment and the planning of a three-day workshop entitled "The Subject Access Problem -- Opportunities for Solution" to be held in October 1978 for a small group of invited participants. One topic for workshop discussion will be the CLR-supported subject access project completed this year at the Syracuse University School of Information Studies.

CONSER COMARC

CLR's involvement in two other cooperative efforts drew to a close during fiscal 1978. Since 1974 CLR has funded and managed the CONSER (Conversion of Serials) project, a shared file-building effort to develop a national data base of serial records using the resources of fourteen North American libraries and the on-line computer facilities of OCLC, Inc. Under CLR management the participating institutions contributed to building a file now containing over 180,000 titles. The Library of Congress and the National Library of Canada have acted as centers of responsibility to ensure the bibliographic quality of the data base. Grants from the National Endowment for the Humanities (NEH), and the National Federation of Abstracting and Indexing Services (through the NSF-funded effort) have enhanced the data base by providing for entry of additional records in the humanities and in science and technology.

Two years ago the Library of Congress agreed to assume responsibility for supporting the system. Fiscal and resources constraints have prevented the Library from sufficiently expanding its automation activities related to CONSER, however, and LC announced that the project will remain at OCLC for the foreseeable future. OCLC will assume the management role previously performed by CLR.

The CONSER project has demonstrated a point basic to the development of a coherent system of national bibliographic control: the quality of a data base can be maintained even if the responsibility for and labor of producing it are shared. A second experimental project in decentralizing labor, COMARC (Cooperative MARC), was also concluded during the past year.

While the CONSER project involved records for serials, COMARC was concerned with extending the Library of Congress's

MARC coverage of books. Under terms of the grant, which began in 1974, LC accepted machine-readable records created locally by selected U.S. libraries and based on LC cataloging copy, removed the duplicates, compared the records with the official catalog, and updated them for consistency when required. The records were then redistributed through the MARC Distribution Service. At the project's end on May 31, 1978, LC had verified 31,660 records.

In discussing the impact of COMARC on the Library, Deputy Librarian of Congress William J. Welsh remarked that "the COMARC experience has been very valuable to LC in enabling it to develop modes of cooperation with outside libraries and network utilities for the building of comprehensive high-quality data bases of bibliographic and authority records. It has helped us better to understand the problems outside libraries have in producing records conforming to LC MARC standards, and to assess the effect of cooperative programs on many aspects of our own operations....Perhaps most important of all, COMARC has had a very positive impact on the attitudes of the library community toward national cooperation in an automated environment.

Cooperation Through Networks

In the library world, the present decade might well be labeled the "decade of cooperation." The attitudes noted above are an outgrowth of the several years of experience libraries have now had with automated bibliographic networks, often referred to as bibliographic utilities. The Council has in the past contributed to the development of most of the existing networks. During the past year, grants were still active at OCLC, Inc. (formerly the Ohio College Library Center), the University of Chicago, and the BALLOTS (Bibliographic Automation of Large Library Operations Using a Time-sharing System) Center at Stanford University. At the year's close, final reports had

been received from OCLC and Chicago and one was shortly expected from BALLOTS. Although another network, MINITEX, had hoped to develop a pilot project that could serve as an initial component of a national serials location system, planning for the project, for which CLR had made a small grant last year, has had to be postponed.

The most recent grant to OCLC, Inc. enabled it to contract with the consulting firm of Arthur D. Little, Inc. for a study of OCLC's future governance and organization. Following receipt of the A. D. Little report, A New Governance Structure for OCLC: Principles and Recommendations (November, 1977), the Ohio members adopted a new governance structure. In addition to changing the name, the membership of the Board of Trustees was expanded and made national in its composition. A new entity called the OCLC Users Council, whose members are elected by participating libraries, was also established.

CLR has supported the development of the University of Chicago's Library Data Management System since 1970 in cooperation with the National Endowment for the Humanities. The two organizations have contributed a total of \$1,476,925 for implementation of the complex system, initially conceived as a comprehensive system for the use of one institution. This year a fourth CLR award covering the first six months of 1978 primarily addressed work needed to explore ways the system might provide support to a group of research libraries. NEH, several other foundations, and the university itself also contributed to this work. At the conclusion of the grant period, the University of Chicago reported that two major operational systems, the authority system and the general circulation system, had been implemented. Two other implementation planning efforts were also concluded: 1) With MIDLNET (Midwest Region Library Network), a plan was developed to implement network operation with multiple research libraries in order to demonstrate the capabilities of the system. 2) With support from IBM, a plan was prepared for a

joint study by the University of Chicago and the University of Wisconsin-Madison to determine the feasibility of a transferable library network system that could be run on widely available standard hardware and software systems.

The prospects for growth of the BALLOTS Center at Stanford University were enhanced early in 1978 when it was announced that the Research Libraries Group, Inc. (RLG) had selected the utility to supply their on-line bibliographic services. RLG members Yale University, Columbia University, and the New York Public Library are scheduled to be on-line before the end of 1981. BALLOTS is concluding work under the second NEH-CLR matching grant awarded in 1975. The center's current focus is improving the efficiency of the system file and index structure in order to support a larger network of users, enhancing the system to accommodate additional standards and codes as issued and reflected in Library of Congress practice, and expanding the system to support additional LC MARC II formats. An upgrading of the network communications system is also planned.

The development and growth of bibliographic networks are essential steps in the establishment of a national library and information system. Networks are the funnels through which many libraries receive bibliographic information. But unless the efforts of networks are coordinated, the creation of a truly comprehensive national system would be thwarted. For the past two years the Council has supported meetings at the Library of Congress of major network representatives and other interested parties that compose LC's Network Advisory Committee (NAC). NAC has become the vehicle for network-related organizations to work together toward rational plans for network development. CLR has also supported meetings of a NAC subcommittee, the Network Technical Architecture Group (NTAG) composed of technical experts from the major networks. This group is concerned with the technical aspects of linking the networks to the Library of Congress and to each other.

The Importance of Standards

As mentioned earlier, one of the hoped-for results accompanying the establishment of a national periodicals center would be promotion of the use of widely accepted standards in the area of serials cataloging and control. The Council has for many years pressed for the development and voluntary adoption of a variety of codes, definitions, rules, and procedures as a necessary step in the evolution of a national library system. Without common agreement on the form and content of bibliographic records, particularly in an automated environment, successful sharing of them cannot come about.

For more than 25 years, the American National Standards Institute (ANSI) Committee Z39 has played a central role in preparing standards in the areas of library work, documentation, and related publishing practices. CLR, in cooperation with the National Science Foundation, has supported the work of this group since 1961. The National Science Foundation has also provided major funding.

Prompted by the planned retirement on July 1, 1978, of long-time committee chairman Jerrold Orne, professor emeritus of the Department of Library Science at the University of North Carolina, an examination of the committee's operations and administration was undertaken during the past year. A task force sponsored by CLR, NSF, and NCLIS produced a report, "American National Standards Committee Z39: Recommended Future Directions," which recommended substantial changes, including hiring a full-time executive director, electing a chairman of the board, changing the name and scope, and seeking multiple funding sources including, possibly, membership fees. The Council of National Library Associations, which acts as the secretariat for Z39, has implemented most of the recommendations. Office space has been secured at the National Bureau of Standards. Council funding, scheduled to end on June 30, 1978, was extended through August to

cover the transition period. Funds were also supplied from NCLIS. CLR maintains its interest in ANSI Committee Z39 as the principal mechanism for standardization in the library and information field.

Another force for standardization among libraries in the United States, Canada, Great Britain, and several other countries is the Anglo-American Cataloging Rules (AACR), a code that governs the description and form of entry of library materials in individual library catalogs. In 1975 the Council made an award to the American Library Association (ALA) on behalf of the Joint Steering Committee for the Revision of AACR, composed of representatives from ALA, the Canadian Committee on Cataloguing, the (British) Library Association, the British Library, and the Library of Congress. Since publication of the first edition in 1967, the growth of international cataloging standards, the substantial addition to library collections of nonprint materials (slides, cassettes, etc.), and other developments made clear the need for a revision of the rules. In June 1978 the American Library Association reported that it had received the complete and final text of the second edition with publication scheduled for November 1978. A common revision fund to be created from proceeds of the sale of AACR-2, is intended to support ongoing work on the code. CLR has also agreed to fund a meeting in December 1978 at the Library of Congress at which members of the ALA/MARBI (Representation in Machine-Readable Form of Bibliographic Information) committee will consider AACR-2 implications for automated systems.

Thus far, the standards disclosed have applied mostly to the technical processing of library materials and the creation of bibliographic records. The library profession is equally concerned about the broader issue of library resources and services. To this end, the American Library Association has worked on standards for college libraries, for public libraries, and more recently for university libraries. CLR assisted the

latter effort this year when it made a small grant to the Association of Research Libraries in support of a November meeting of the Joint Committee of the Association of Research Libraries and the Association of College and Research Libraries on University Library Standards with representatives of other higher education association and accrediting agencies. The purpose of the meeting was to discuss the Joint Committee's draft university library standards in order to strengthen them and facilitate their national acceptance.

From National to International

The revision of the Anglo-American Cataloging Rules was in the best sense a cooperative international endeavor. The Council's concern with the problems facing libraries has never been restricted to those that affect only libraries in the United States. Indeed, the logical extension of a cooperative national library and information service is an international system made up of national and multinational networks. Efforts toward improving national bibliographic control greatly enhance progress toward development of an international system.

In the present decade the primary channel of Council support for international library cooperation has been through the activities of the International Federation of Library Associations and Institutions (IFLA). With CLR's financial assistance, IFLA has greatly strengthened its administrative and staff operations. In 1976 a reorganization of the federation was approved to include a wide-ranging professional program. Minutes of the 1977 meetings of the new Professional Board demonstrate that the renovated structure has encouraged new initiatives and provided a mechanism through which IFLA can exert stronger leadership and employ more effective use of resources in promoting library interests worldwide.

One of IFLA's major programs is coordinated by its International Office for Universal Bibliographic Control (UBC) which has received separate CLR funding since its establishment in 1974. A successful system of universal bibliographic control, a natural extension of national bibliographic control, requires that each nation assume the responsibility for preparing and making available bibliographic records of its own publications utilizing accepted standards to ensure that the records can be readily used in manual and machine-readable systems anywhere in the world.

The UBC office acts as a catalyst and coordinator of practical activities designed to achieve this somewhat rarefied goal. Thus the office acts as a secretariat to working groups and individuals engaged in special bibliographic projects, collects and disseminates information related to bibliographic standards, coordinates meetings of national and international cataloging and bibliographic organizations, and edits and publishes a variety of papers on standards and other bibliographic matters. Chief among its activities of the past year was the organization and planning of the International Congress on National Bibliographies sponsored by UNESCO and held in Paris in September 1977.

Although IFLA has received the bulk of the Council's support allocated for international projects in recent years, it is not alone in trying to further the interests of the library and information community on a global scale. This year marked the end of a CLR grant to strengthen the secretariat of another important international organization, the International Council on Archives (ICA). During the three years of grant support, ICA revised its constitution and dues structure, extended its membership geographically, established regional branches and professional committees, and implemented a variety of projects and publications designed to assist archival development throughout the world.

Although the interests of the U.S. library and information communities are represented through their membership in such bodies as IFLA and ICA, little significant attempt has been made to coordinate the efforts of various sectors of the communities within an international framework. UNESCO projects and activities have received much financial support from the U. S. government, foundations, educational institutions, and individuals, yet U.S. influence within the UNESCO structure has never been strong.

As an attempt to improve this situation, initiative was taken in the past year to form a U.S. National Committee for the UNESCO General Program to serve as the central coordinating body of the U.S. national information community, responsible for representing and promoting its needs, interests, and views primarily with respect to the UNESCO General Information Program. The American Library Association has agreed to provide for one year a temporary headquarters and secretariat for the committee while organizers seek a permanent sponsoring organization. CLR has made a small grant to ALA to cover its expense in this endeavor.

While the establishment of the national committee will provide an organized forum for promoting the views of the U.S. library and information community, the efforts of individuals to exchange information across national boundaries cannot be discounted. CLR has from time to time found it possible to assist these individual efforts by helping to defray travel costs incurred by U.S. librarians who have leadership responsibilities in international gatherings. Funds for this activity have diminished in recent years, and the Council is at present reviewing its policy in this area. Nevertheless during fiscal 1978 small contributions were made to assist the president of the Association for Recorded Sound Collections in giving a paper on U.S. broadcast sound archives at a gathering of the European Broadcasting Union Sound Archive Experts in Lisbon in July 1978.

Likewise the chairperson of the Music Library Association Subcommittee on Musics Other than Western-Art was given a small grant to assist in her attendance at the 1978 annual conference of the International Association of Music Libraries where she reported on her compilation of a thesaurus of terms for musics other than Western-art. In addition some assistance was given to a professor of the faculty of the University of Hawaii at Manoa Graduate School of Library Studies to make a study tour of libraries and information services in the South Pacific. Finally, three U.S. librarians received funds to allow for their participation in an International Seminar on the Public Library and the Adult Independent Learner, sponsored by the Public Library Research Group in England. The three were active members of the Consortium for Public Library Innovation, an earlier CLR-assisted project.

PLANNING FOR INSTITUTIONAL CHANGE

The previous chapter spoke of a set of national activities that have the potential of assisting large numbers of libraries to perform more effectively and efficiently. These programs have come about not only as a way of relieving some of the financial and social pressures on libraries, but also to improve the nation's capacity to use its information resources. To take advantage of national services, however, libraries must first evaluate their individual missions and goals and create in themselves the capacity to adapt to new circumstances and to meet new demands. This is particularly true of academic and research libraries, the Council's principal concern, many of which are struggling in concert with their parent institutions to combat a general depression in higher education. The extraordinary surge in funding, growth, and development that followed World War II and continued in the fifties had leveled off by the end of the sixties and now, in the seventies, has actually gone into a decline.

The impact of this situation is clearly evident in the issues surrounding the related areas of library management,

services, and collection development. Library managers are being asked to produce evidence of cost effectiveness of services. Acquisition funds are no longer adequate to maintain collection growth -- indeed, even to maintain a status quo. Fees are being established by some institutions for such services as interlibrary loan that formerly were considered a collegial courtesy if not a responsibility. And librarians, through unions and by other means, are collectively asking for more of a share in determining goals and setting priorities. It is a stressful situation, and stress provokes change.

In the last ten years, the Council has initiated a number of programs to help academic libraries become more effective partners in the educational process by assessing their needs and planning for change in a constructive fashion. By the end of the fiscal year, plans were being laid to capitalize on the experience gained in these programs and extend it in a more coordinated way to a larger number of academic institutions (see chapter 4). As in other areas of the Council's program, the year that ended June 30, 1978, was a time of consolidation and transition.

Library Management

Previous reports have described in some detail the Council's 1968 initiation of a long-range program to assist academic and research libraries achieve management excellence. In recent years the primary catalyst for management activities has been the CLR-supported Office of Management Studies (OMS), established within the Association of Research Libraries in 1970. The office also receives support from other foundations, from the sale of its publications and services, and from ARL itself.

OMS staff work with academic libraries to develop practical methods for improving library performance. CLR funds have supported the development of two of its major programs of assistance: the Management Review and Analysis Program and the Academic Library Development Program (the latter was developed outside of the OMS office with OMS staff assistance but has now been integrated into the regular OMS operation). A third, the Collection Analysis Project, is supported by the Andrew W. Mellon Foundation and focuses on materials selection, acquisition, retention, and preservation policies of research libraries.

The Management Review and Analysis Program (MRAP) presents a framework within which large academic and research library staffs analyze their management systems to identify strengths and weaknesses and to outline areas for action and change. To carry out the rigorous MRAP self-study, a team is appointed that examines the library's decision-making process over a nine- to twelve-month period and recommends the organizational changes that are needed to improve day-to-day operations and to plan effectively for the future. Thus far 24 academic and research libraries have used the program, the most current participants being the University of Oklahoma Libraries and the Southern Illinois University Library at Edwardsville.

In 1975 the Council initiated the Academic Library Development Program (ALDP) in the belief that smaller libraries could also benefit from looking closely at how they are meeting the needs of the campus community and then finding ways to improve services to their users. The University of North Carolina at Charlotte provided the site for a pilot project during which procedures and resource materials were developed similar to those used in MRAP but geared especially to the small- to medium-sized academic library. At the conclusion of the pilot project the Council allocated funds for a testing and evaluation

phase. Several institutions of varying sizes (Carnegie-Mellon University, the University of Wisconsin-Parkside, Drew University) were awarded grants to conduct self-analyses using the ALDP manual and the services of the OMS staff. In March 1978 Seattle University also entered the program as an example of a smaller academic library with a staff size of under 25.

In addition to these assisted programs of library self-studies, major aspects of the OMS program include information collection and dissemination and a library staff training program. OMS operates the Systems and Procedures Exchange Center (SPEC), a clearinghouse of information on current management practices of member libraries. SPEC staff survey ARL libraries on specific issues and report the survey results in two-page SPEC Flyers, backed up by a selection of illustrative documents in SPEC Kits. Recent topics have included automated circulation systems, automated acquisitions, and the changing role of personnel officers. The OMS staff training program continued to expand during the year to include special focus workshops, generally two-day sessions conducted at a specific library and focused on a particular need such as communication skills. Library Management Skills Institutes, increasingly successful laboratory experiences for budding library administrators, were held in Kansas City, Missouri, Columbia, Maryland, and Chicago.

Library Services

If a library is well-managed, that fact will be most readily reflected in its services. How well are academic libraries serving their various publics -- students, faculty, administrators, and more and more often, the surrounding community? How effectively are they participating in the teaching and learning process? This question, which had

concerned the Council for some time, was the stimulus for the initiation in 1969 of the College Library Program, an effort to get administrators and teaching faculty members as well as librarians to take a fresh look at how the library should function in the academic community. Jointly sponsored by CLR and the National Endowment for the Humanities, the College Library Program enables libraries in four-year accredited colleges and universities to implement a broad range of activities that link library services and classroom instruction. Each institution is required to allocate funds over and beyond the regular library budget to share the cost of the total program, which may last from three to five years.

The five grants awarded during 1977-78 and described below bring to 32 the number of institutions that have received funding for College Library Program activities.

At Ball State University (Indiana) a Course-Related Library Instruction Program will build on a 1975 pilot project and involve the English and history departments. The three-year program will be directed by a Library Instruction Task Force composed of librarians, faculty members, and students.

DePauw University (Indiana) will expand to upper classmen a program started for freshmen under a 1976-77 CLR Library Service Enhancement Program award. Faculty members will receive small grants to work with librarians in order to develop library-related components to be introduced into the regular academic curriculum. Doctoral students from nearby Indiana University's Instructional Systems Technology Division will also aid in the design.

At Salem State College in Salem, Massachusetts, the three-year grant will provide two librarian-teachers who will work with humanities faculty in an interdisciplinary program, develop a directory of local and regional resources to augment the humanities curriculum, and establish a student peer-tutoring program for assistance in library research.

The three-year award at the University of Toledo (Ohio) will support its Bibliographic Instruction Program in the College of Education. Using a self-paced instructional workbook and other curricular materials, the program will involve all undergraduate education students.

The University of Wisconsin-Parkside's three-year Bibliographic Instruction Program builds on a basic library skills program in which all students are required to participate. Among other activities, the library staff hopes to produce specialized workbooks for teaching advanced library skills to undergraduate majors in each of seven disciplines.

In April 1978 CLR and NEH received another group of applications from which winners will be selected and announced in the fall of 1978. At the end of the fiscal year, CLR and NEH reached a mutual decision that the College Library Program in its present form would be discontinued. Previously, it was announced that an allied program, the Council's Library Service Enhancement

Program, also would no longer be offered. Elements of both programs, however, are to be incorporated in the new effort directed toward academic libraries described in the final chapter.

An outgrowth of one of the earliest College Library Program awards is Project LOEX (Library Orientation-Instruction Exchange), an international clearinghouse for materials and information concerning library instruction and orientation located at Eastern Michigan University. Established in 1972, Project LOEX moved well on its way to becoming self-supporting during the past year when it instituted a membership fee. As of June 30, 1978, when the Council's funding ended, over 300 libraries had become LOEX members. Over the years members have contributed over 12,000 items to the project's circulating collection. Project LOEX continues to be a leader in the movement to promote the ideas and practical knowledge needed to carry out programs of academic library instruction.

Library Needs and Collections

In order to successfully plan for future change, libraries need to know first where they stand today and second what the needs of their patrons are. Only after a careful assessment can they begin to build collections and services that meet the needs of students, scholars, researchers and even the merely curious. From time to time the Council has supported surveys and status reports considered to be of value to the profession. For example, in 1968 a small grant to the American Association of Law Libraries enabled that organization to conduct a survey of U.S. and Canadian law library resources; grant funds continue to support the activity which has become an annual report published in the May issue of Law Library Journal. A final report this past year concluded a grant awarded in 1974 to the New York State

Library to study New York State's official library and information resources in the Albany area. The goal of the project was to assess how the State Library could improve its information services to the state government, including executive agencies and legislative and judicial bodies. Direct outgrowths of the study were the publication by the State Library of Information Resources of Selected New York State Agencies and the formation of the New York State Interdepartmental Information Group to improve communication. This group also plans a study concerning the control and availability of state agency publications.

A new grant was awarded this year to the Office for Advancement of Public Negro Colleges to prepare a follow-up study to an earlier CLR-funded survey of the status of libraries of the 34 black public colleges and universities in the United States. It is expected that this report will be helpful, as was the first, in determining whether the libraries are growing at a rate commensurate with student growth in their institutions.

Another new grant went to the University of California, Berkeley, for support of a national shelflist measurement project. Project designers plan to analyze and publish the results of the 1977 shelflist measurement undertaken by the Chief Collection Development Officers of Large Research Libraries, an ALA-affiliated group, in order to enable the participants to analyze their own collections and collecting strengths in each subject area. Allied goals are to provide an analysis of national and regional collecting strengths and weaknesses and to improve coordination of collecting efforts among major research libraries. A conversion table will be developed to allow for the measurement of collections that are classified in the Dewey Decimal system rather than the Library of Congress classification.

Of course, the end result of improving collections is to make them more useful for library patrons. Access to a library's collection has traditionally been provided through card or book catalogs that contain an individual record for each item in the collection. As collections have grown, the corresponding catalogs have swelled to unwieldy proportions, especially in terms of maintenance. In recent years technical innovation has presented an attractive alternative to the traditional catalog format: computer output microfilm (COM). COM appears to combine the best features of microforms (low-cost production and size) and computer technology (speed). A COM-produced catalog can be quickly and easily updated and reissued at intervals to provide the most current information to librarians.

Because of the rising interest of libraries in COM for catalog and other applications, in 1976 the Council brought together a panel of micrographics and computer experts to establish the specifics of an inquiry into the degree to which COM hardware, software, and services could be effectively applied to library operations. The resulting report, Computer-Output Microfilm: Its Library Applications by William Saffady was published by the American Library Association in the spring. Reflecting the state of the art of COM technology through January 1978, the report is designed for library personnel, including systems analysts, administrators, and others who need an understanding of the latest developments in COM equipment, software, applications, and systems design.

PROFESSIONAL DEVELOPMENT

To celebrate the centennial of the American Library Association in 1976, its official journal published a series of profiles of individual working librarians. "Who We Are" presented a kaleidoscope of library specializations, as varied as human interests, that occupy the nation's 115,000 professional librarians. The article's lasting impression is of the vast store of knowledge and skill that librarians must carry daily to their places of work.

The need for librarians to continue to upgrade their knowledge and skills has never been more critical. The need to attract talented individuals to the profession and to provide continuing opportunities for professional growth and enrichment in order to keep them -- in short to nurture their talents -- has never been greater. With the profession's national attention currently focused on this issue, librarians are finding increased opportunities for continuing education. Academic librarians have created a mechanism through which to concentrate their efforts within the Association of College and Research Libraries, which has established a Continuing Education Committee to develop a program that would assist ACRL members in their professional growth.

The Council's interest in professional development dates from 1969 when the CLR Fellowship Program was first offered. In the year covered by this report, 15 fellowships and internships were awarded to individual librarians on a competitive basis. In addition to the Fellowship Program and the Academic Library Management Internship Program, the Council agreed to administer an internship program, under contract with the National Library of Medicine, for health sciences librarians. A small grant was also made to the Catholic University of America on behalf of CLENE (Continuing Library Education Network and Exchange) as partial support for a national meeting held in June 1978 to establish a voluntary continuing education recognition system for librarians.

The more the profession learns about its composition, of course, the better it should be able to recruit qualified individuals. In September 1977 the American Library Association successfully sought Council funds for a project to collect data on the ethnic and sexual composition of the library workforce. Many discipline-related and professional associations provide this sort of data for their members as an aid to planning affirmative action programs.

ALA's Office for Library Personnel Resources will work closely on the project with the Survey Research Laboratory of the University of Illinois. The survey population will be all public, academic, and school libraries profiled by the National Center for Education Statistics. The survey is scheduled for completion in late 1978.

Academic Library Management Intern Program

Three women were selected to participate in the fifth year of the Council's Academic Library Management Intern Program.

Beginning in the fall of 1978, each will spend the academic year working with the director and top administrative staff of one of the country's important academic libraries selected for its recognized administrative excellence. As in past years, the interns receive an amount equal to the normal basic salary and benefits (up to \$20,000) that were paid by their employers in the 1977-78 academic year.

Surviving the rigorous competition, which included personal interviews, were Joan L. Chambers, Sandra S. Coleman, and Sara C. Heitshu.

Joan L. Chambers, head, Government Publications Department, University of Nevada, Reno, Library, will intern with Connie Dunlap, Duke University library director. Ms. Chambers received a B.A. from the University of Northern Colorado (1958) and an M.L.S. from the University of California at Berkeley (1970). In 1976, she was the first Reno library faculty member to be elected to the faculty senate and was subsequently elected chairman.

Sandra S. Coleman, head, Reference Department, University of New Mexico General Library, will spend her year working with David Weber, director of the Stanford University Libraries. Ms. Coleman is a 1966 graduate of Eckerd College in St. Petersburg, Florida, and received an M.L.S. from Indiana University in 1970. Prior to her present position she had a variety of positions in the University of New Mexico School of Law Library.

Sara C. Heitshu, assistant head, Book Purchasing and Business Operations, University of Michigan Library, will intern with John McDonald, director of the University of Connecticut Library. Ms. Heitshu, a 1965 graduate of St. Lawrence University, received an A.M.L.S. from the University of Michigan in 1969. She remained at Michigan and moved to her present position in 1973.

Health Sciences Library Management Intern Program

Like the program above, the Health Sciences Library Management Intern Program is designed to increase the number of librarians who, in addition to having the intellect, personality, and character required for director-level positions in academic health sciences libraries, also have a firm grounding in management processes and techniques. The program is funded by the National Library of Medicine (NLM) and administered by the Council.

Interns receive stipends (up to \$25,000) that cover their basic salary and benefits received during 1977-78. In addition to working with the director of a major academic health sciences library, the interns will spend some time at the National Library of Medicine.

In this first year of the program, applications were received from 34 candidates. Seven finalists were invited to Washington for interviews. The successful applicants were Carol G. Jenkins, William E. Maina, and Faith A. Meakin.

Carol G. Jenkins, is director of the Dental Library at the University of Oregon, Health Sciences Center. She will intern with Nancy Lorenzi, director of the Medical Center Libraries, University of Cincinnati. Ms. Jenkin received a B.A. in English from Kalamazoo College in 1968 and an M.L.S. from the University of Oregon in 1972. In addition to directing the activities of the Dental Library, she is the codirector of the Division of Educational Resources with the responsibility of promoting the development and use of educationally sound instructional materials.

William E. Maina is the coordinator of the Library Computerized Literature Searching Service at the University of California, San Diego. He will intern with Samuel Hitt, director

of the Health Sciences Library, University of North Carolina. Mr. Maina received a B.A. in English (1970) and an M.L.S. (1971) from the University of California, Berkeley. The following year he participated in a graduate training program in medical librarianship at the UCLA Biomedical Library. Mr. Maina began his career in 1972 as a reference librarian at the Biomedical Library in his present institution. In 1975 he was selected to introduce the use of computerized bibliographic retrieval systems to the entire university library system.

Faith A. Meakin is head of the Biomedical Library Reference Department at the University of California, San Diego. She will intern with Glenn Brudvig, director of the Bio-Medical Library, University of Minnesota. Ms. Meakin received a B.A. in English (1965) and an M.L.S. (1966) from Syracuse University. The next year she worked at the UCLA Biomedical Library under a public health service internship in medical librarianship and in 1967 moved to her present position in San Diego. In 1974 she served as president of the statewide Librarians Association of the University of California.

Fellowship Program

The oldest of the Council's professional development programs, the CLR Fellowship Program has assisted the professional growth of over 200 librarians. The award covers costs (exclusive of salary) incident to a self-developed research project aimed at improving the fellow's knowledge of the substantive issues affecting librarianship. The fellowship is not intended to support work toward an advanced degree nor to assist activities that are operational in nature or of only local utility. As in past years, this year's nine fellows have selected topics that range widely in the field, from collection

development in academic health sciences libraries to the organization of public libraries.

Virginia M. Bowden, assistant to the library director, University of Texas Health Science Center at San Antonio, will study current monograph collection development in academic health sciences libraries to include the identification of current trends and institutional variables and the establishment of a base line for future comparisons.

Jay B. Clark, chief of technical services, Houston Public Library, will study technical and political problems in selected computer-based networks of public libraries similar to that planned for the Houston metropolitan area.

Florence Kell Doksansky, assistant librarian, Rotch Library, Massachusetts Institute of Technology, will make a comparative study of staff development practices in several major academic libraries.

Wayne Gossage, library director, Bank Street College of Education, New York City, will study education library services of 23 leading research universities.

Hugo Kunoff, subject librarian for modern languages, Indiana University, will study the emergence of research as a major responsibility of universities and its early impact on academic libraries.

Mary Drake McFeely, head, Reference Department, Smith College Library, will prepare a bibliography on women and work in the United States and England from 1890 through World War I.

Dorothy A. Pearson, serials librarian, Princeton University, will study the current organizational structure of and within technical services departments in large research libraries.

W. Boyd Rayward, assistant professor, Graduate Library School, University of Chicago, will study the organization and administration of large public libraries and public library systems.

Jean F. Trumbore, associate reference librarian, University of Delaware, will undertake a two-month internship in the documents section of the Pattee Library, Pennsylvania State University, to improve her skills in the administration of an academic documents collection and a one-month internship at the Congressional Research Service, Library of Congress, to gain on-the-job experience in legislative reference work.

New England Academic Librarians' Writing Seminar

The past fiscal year was an active one for the **New England Academic Librarians' Writing Seminar**, established in August 1976 with CLR funds. The program treats writing as "a planned and organized activity" with opportunities for the ten participants to exchange ideas and review and criticize each other's work. Products of the seminar have appeared regularly in a column entitled "On Our Minds -- Writer's Seminar" that appears in the Journal of Academic Librarianship. A book of essays to be published by Scarecrow Press is also planned.

THE YEAR AHEAD

Continuity of purpose is the dominant characteristic of research libraries and by extension of the Council itself. It is especially true that programs recently established or projected for the near future are possible only because of what has gone before. Foundations have been built for many of the key components of a nationwide and even international system to provide library support for research and advanced instruction. The time has now come to build the structure itself. The year or, more accurately, the years ahead will be devoted to that task.

The principles enumerated when the Council was formed remain unchanged. The underlying concern is for the users of libraries and the focus is still on research libraries, because the quality of their performance is of importance to all libraries and all who depend on them. The methods employed are research, development, demonstration, and dissemination; the means are still grants to others and direct staff effort in selected areas. The long-range prospects for progress still acknowledge the importance of coordinating efforts to develop resources and

services and of promoting international approaches to finding solutions to many of the most fundamental problems. The magnitude of the undertaking we see for ourselves is almost overwhelming and the effort required is justified only by its importance to scholarship, to the economic and operational well being of universities, and to a society that is increasingly dependent for its survival on the growing store of knowledge and information.

We have no delusions about our role. The Council, by itself, can accomplish little. Further, no other interested or responsible organization, regardless of its stature or mandate, can by itself do all that is required. The work that lies ahead will call for energy, imagination, and careful thought by many individuals who personally understand and collectively assume responsibility for the goal of bringing into being the key functional components of a nationwide research support system.

The Council sees several parts it should play in the overall effort. Drawing on advice from many individuals, it can help describe the need, it can help assemble at least some of the funds that are required, it can assist in coordinating the work of key contributors to the overall effort and can undertake itself or otherwise support some of the many specific tasks that need to be done. The Council will continue to act directly when appropriate, but will take most seriously its obligation to promote purposeful change by serving as a catalyst, by consolidating the efforts of others, and by providing a reflective surface to be used by all who would monitor progress and assess results.

Several familiar, primary topics will dominate the Council's immediate future, just as they have its past. Included on the CLR list of priorities are bibliographic control, collection building, library management, professional education, and

analysis and planning. The approaches we will take to address each of these subjects will vary and some of them will be new. Limited total resources and less "discretionary" funding than has been available in the past combine to force increased precision in targeting both grants and staff activity. Our end objective is to promote purposeful and productive change in academic and research libraries, to encourage actions that contribute to the well-being of those libraries, and, most of all, to help ensure that the obligations of those libraries are in fact thoroughly and carefully fulfilled.

Turning briefly to the topics themselves, let us note the status of each as the year begins. In this way we can provide some sense of the activity that lies ahead and a backdrop for the report to be prepared a year from now.

Bibliographic Control

A major effort to develop and establish a computerized bibliographic system is underway. During the last decade libraries and other organizations have embarked on a complex undertaking to apply computer technology to technical operations and to certain service activities. Progress has been substantial. Many internal functions, especially in large research libraries, have been automated; several networks have been established to provide cataloging services; progress has been made in developing standards for the form and content of bibliographic records; and a large number of bibliographic data bases have been made available for users on a commercial basis.

The Library of Congress, OCLC, Inc., and a few universities (Stanford and Chicago for example) have by research and experiment taken the lead in developing an understanding of the

technical issues. The National Library of Medicine has moved rapidly and imaginatively to develop and provide computer-based bibliographic services in a specialized subject field. These and other examples, while important and useful of themselves, have also served to underscore the magnitude and complexity of the real task of transforming in productive ways many of the elements of the library and information structure of the country. Much of the past activity, understandably, can be characterized as a set of independent, largely unrelated efforts, each plowing new ground, without any carefully described and commonly accepted overall national plan to which the individual projects might relate and contribute.

An improved planning effort stimulated by CLR and the Library of Congress has recently begun. The time has now come to capitalize on past investments and embark on a program of development work that will result in a nationwide computerized bibliographic system for libraries, one that will (a) improve the operating performance of individual libraries, (b) extend access to comprehensive bibliographic records to all who need such information, and (c) permit the development of new approaches to identifying and locating recorded information, nationally and internationally.

Much attention has been given the subject of supervising and monitoring the progress of this new development effort. Working with the Library of Congress and the National Commission on Libraries and Information Science, CLR will assume administrative responsibility for the overall development program. Guidance will be sought from leaders of existing computerized library networks and representatives of university, library, and scholarly communities. In terms of formal structure a management committee will be established, to be assisted by an advisory group composed of the best and most effective leaders in research library automation and in library, network, and university

operations. Primary policy directions will be reviewed by advisors from the world of scholarship and from the ranks of university and library administrators and trustees.

It is planned to involve the Library of Congress and such existing primary networks as the Research Libraries Group/BALLOTS, OCLC, Inc., and the Washington Library Network in the development work to help support further refinement of these existing services and to promote their integration into the national system. Specialists in fields of computing, communications, and management will also be involved. The Council will assign a program officer to the management committee as project administrator. The funding plan is based on a cooperative effort by a group of private foundations and other organizations to meet the total cost for the four- to five-year effort, estimated at about \$6,000,000.

Collection Building

The Council has never been able to support collection development or preservation programs at individual libraries. It has supported analysis and research designed to address some underlying problems and questions related to creating and maintaining resource strength nationally. Research into the full range of preservation-related matters provides an example of CLR involvement and support over many years. The most recent Council activity in this area is the preparation of the technical plan for a national periodicals center. Specific action to be taken in the future is not yet certain, but there are many issues of importance. Assessing the concept of "national collections," understanding better the relationship between proximity of materials and their utilization, improving methods for assessing collection strength, investigating the effect of improved bibliographic control on the level of demand for

materials, and establishing the strategies for cooperative action in resource development and preservation are but a few. Somehow we will seek to add to the understanding of these topics in order to assist those who set priorities and provide funds for collections and their maintenance.

Library Management

For nearly a decade, the Council has supported or directly managed a number of programs designed to improve library management. Results have been substantial for both individual libraries and the profession. The ultimate goal of CLR efforts in this area is not to develop skills in management methods for their own sake but rather to find and use management techniques appropriate to academic and research libraries as a means of improving the quality and expanding the scope of library service and of promoting efficiency and economy in internal operations.

At the close of the fiscal year, plans were completed for a new effort directed toward academic and research libraries, to be called the Academic Library Program (ALP). Funded by CLR, ARL, and several other foundations, the program will be administered by the ARL Office of Management Studies and will build upon their tested programs -- MRAP, ALDP, and the Collection Analysis Project -- described earlier. In addition to these tested programs, the ALP will develop other self-study modules including:

A Small Library Planning Program. This self-study procedure will enable the very small library to sharpen understanding of its role in the academic community and to present an action plan for improving its performance in supporting instructional activities.

A Services Development Program. The purpose of this program will be to help libraries examine critically the quality of performance of such services as reference, circulation, interlibrary loan, reserve book, and bibliographic instruction. This program will draw upon the experience gained in recent years from the College Library Program, jointly sponsored by the Council on Library Resources and the National Endowment for the Humanities, and the Council's own Library Service Enhancement Program.

An Organizational Screening Program. This program will help libraries conduct a rapid assessment of their current situation to determine the need for more comprehensive analysis and substantial change.

Council support for ALP is intended to extend the influence of OMS programs to two- and four-year liberal arts colleges as well as universities, thus opening an additional path to link functionally libraries with related missions. The program will be advanced by training as many as 100 working librarians to serve as consultants in one or another of several fields (e.g., collection development, instructional service, data processing, personnel training, etc.). These consultants, assisted by OMS staff and making use of a variety of specially prepared materials, will enable a large number of libraries to embark on their own assisted self-studies, each one designed to address specific problems or areas of interest.

The benefits of this approach are many. First, the process furnishes a comprehensive review of key areas and enables the library to establish appropriate priorities based upon thorough analysis. Further, the approach focuses on producing positive, concrete, long-term results. Staff involvement in the analysis promotes assumption of responsibility by individuals for

providing solutions to problems and for making needed change. The assistance provided in the program -- the methodology, the manual and other materials, the consultation -- enables the library to obtain an objective assessment of its situation. Finally, the program acknowledges that differences occur among various interest groups within the institution and the library and furnishes a methodology for dealing constructively with those differences.

While ALP is the primary Council-supported program concerned with management improvement, opportunities for additional productive work on several specific topics will be pursued as well.

Professional Education

Since 1969, with the creation of the Fellowship Program, the Council has promoted and supported a number of activities to add to the skills and perceptions of professional staff members. Experimental programs to support professional education for subject specialists and advanced work in a subject field for librarians, support for staff development programs through workshops and other means, the Council's Academic Library Management Intern Program, and the CLR-administered counterpart for health sciences librarians are all examples of CLR activity.

Despite these successful programs, a conviction persists that the broader topic of basic professional education for academic and research librarians is one that needs attention. Academic and research libraries are distinctive organizations operating in a demanding and changing environment. The present nature of both the obligations and operations of these libraries suggests that an examination of the skills required of managers and administrators and the methods used to provide those skills should be reviewed and possibly changed.

Individual schools periodically assess their goals and methods, but there is some indication that the time is ripe for an across-the-board review. The subject is one of great and, we think, fundamental importance. We are by no means certain how it should be approached, but the topic is clearly one for future attention.

Analysis and Planning

In recent years, there has been substantial work done to recast the way in which academic and research libraries operate internally and simultaneously to change the ways these libraries work together as they seek to improve their performance in supporting research and instruction. Despite this intense effort, there is still no adequate overall strategy for the development of a cohesive national library system, especially that portion designed to support advanced instruction, research, and scholarship. The failure to establish clearly and to articulate effectively the direction in which these libraries are going creates confusion among administrators and users alike and is an impediment to effective and decisive action. In almost every discussion of problem areas where work seems required, the lack of sufficient factual information pertinent to the issue at hand is apparent. Further, a much-needed capacity for collective action by these libraries has not developed, in part because there is no credible base of data or fully accepted statement of priorities on which to build.

For a combination of reasons, including escalating costs, expanding areas of service responsibility, and both the potential impact and unique characteristics of computing technology, it is imperative that prompt action be taken to build the foundation for a transformed system and to establish the methods for making change. The nature of anticipated changes will, in one way or

another, affect in important ways the users of libraries as well as those responsible for their operation. Too much is at stake to move precipitously and without sufficient understanding, but the evidence is strong that fundamental decisions are being taken without an adequate factual and analytical underpinning. What seems essential at this point, if libraries are to fulfill their obligations responsibly and in a financially acceptable way, is a far more sophisticated approach to reviewing library operations, an improved understanding of the processes of information organization and use, and better methods for establishing the fiscal and human requirements needed to make change and to provide a planned and durable transformation.

The general idea of a more formal approach to analysis and planning is not yet fully refined, nor are the methods established. The principal objective is to develop a structured, carefully monitored, and purposefully organized program of research and evaluation to replace the present ad hoc approach to resolving key issues or establishing new directions, often without appropriate information and substantive review.

These then are some targets for attention. They are set not by the Council itself but rather by the circumstances in which academic and research libraries find themselves today. As it has in the past, the Council will persist in its fundamental goal, which is to help research libraries help themselves. Even after twenty-two years, it is a task that seems well worth the effort.

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¹Mr. Haas was elected at the November 1977 annual meeting to succeed Dr. Cole as CLR president on January 1, 1978.

²Until his death, February 22, 1978.

³Until his retirement December 31, 1977.

⁴Ms. Ackerman was elected to succeed Dr. Hard at the November 1977 annual meeting.

⁵Established at the November 1977 annual meeting.

⁶Through June 30, 1978.

⁷As of May 1978.

⁸Until his death, December 26, 1977.

⁹As of July 1978.

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"Minutes of Meetings of the Network Technical Architecture Group, August-November 1977." (January 20, 1978): 66-68.

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Smith, Jessie Carney. Black Academic Libraries and Research Collections: An Historical Survey. Westport, Conn.: Greenwood Press, 1977.

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Council On Library Resources, Inc.

CLR-SUPPORTED PROJECTS ACTIVE IN FISCAL 1978

	FY 1978			
	Unpaid 6/30/77	Grants (Adjustments)	Payments (Refunds)	Unpaid 6/30/78
American Association of Law Libraries, Committee on Statistics, Washington, D.C. Survey of U.S. and Canadian law library resources (\$20,000-1968)	\$ 3,419	\$ (419)	\$ 1,000	\$ 2,000
American Library Association, Chicago, Ill. Ethnic and sexual composition/salary survey for librarians	-0-	13,856	2,000	11,856
Revision of <u>Anglo-American Cataloging Rules</u> (\$111,432-1975)	22,228	(10,141)	15,000 (2,913)	-0-
Secretariat for the U.S. National Committee for the UNESCO General Information Program (USNC/UNESCO-PGI)	-0-	2,500	-0-	2,500
Etta Arntzen, Athens, Ga. Revision of <u>Guide to Art Reference Books</u> (\$8,000-1971)	1,600	-0-	1,600	-0-
Association of Research Libraries, Washington, D.C. Academic Library Program	-0-	326,500	-0-	326,500
Office of University Library Management Studies (\$81,136-1974; \$210,000-1975)	79,000	-0-	56,000	23,000
University library standards meeting	-0-	4,000 (288)	3,712	-0-

	FY 1978			
	Unpaid 6/30/77	Grants (Adjustments)	Payments (Refunds)	Unpaid 6/30/78
W. J. Barrow Research Laboratory, Inc., Richmond, Va. Research on preservation of books and other library materials (\$240,000-1975)	25,583	(18,854)	9,428 (2,699)	-0-
Bibliothèque Royale Albert Ier, Brussels. Preparation of Belgian exhibit	-0-	2,000	-0-	2,000
Boston Theological Institute, Cambridge, Mass. ISSNs for theological serials (\$1,000-1975; \$1,200-1976)	1,200	-0-	1,200	-0-
Catholic University of America, Washington, D.C., National meeting on continuing education for librarians	-0-	500	500	-0-
Consortium for Public Library Innovation, Tulsa, Ok. Support of the Consortium's research study group (\$10,930-1976)	3,730	(1,325)	2,405	-0-
Assistance for Consortium members to attend a British seminar on the public library and the adult independent learner	-0-	1,770	1,770	-0-
Council-administered Projects Academic Library Development Program				
Carnegie-Mellon University (\$21,000-1977)	16,500	-0-	13,500	3,000
Drew University	-0-	18,845	15,200	3,645
North Carolina Central University; for project coordinator (\$73,527-1977)	48,742	-0-	40,785	7,957
Seattle University	-0-	15,510	4,750	10,760

	FY 1978			
	Unpaid 6/30/77	Grants (Adjustments)	Payments (Refunds)	Unpaid 6/30/78
University of Wisconsin- Parkside (\$21,350-1977)	21,350	-0-	9,000	12,350
Academic Library Management Intern Program (\$100,000-1974; \$265,000-1975; \$110,000-1976)	5,299	(1,234)	4,065	-0-
1977-78 (\$98,330-1977)	98,330	-0-	83,519	14,811
1978-79	-0-	65,000	-0-	65,000
Advanced Study Program for Librarians (\$115,000-1975)	9,710	(3,232)	6,478	-0-
1977-78 (\$73,092-1977)	73,042	-0-	62,033	11,009
CONSER Project (\$250,000-1975)	57,051	-0-	22,954 (8,676)	42,773
Fellowship Program through September 1977	14,771	(7,528)	5,998	
1977-78 (\$51,025-1977)	39,025	(2,843)	(215) 29,713	1,460 6,469
1978-79	-0-	28,911	6,600	22,311
Library Service Enhancement Program				
1976-77 (\$220,000-1976)	32,761	(14,773)	19,010 (1,022)	-0-
1977-78 (\$194,857-1977)	177,280		134,528	42,752
Travel by U.S. librarians for purposes important to profession	824	1,750 (770)	1,808 (4)	-0-
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J. Periam Danton, Berkeley, Calif.				
Completion of supplement, 1966-75, of <u>Index to Fest- schriften in Librarianship</u> (\$500-1976)	100	-0-	100	-0-
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Robert B. Downs, Urbana, Ill.				
Guide to library resources in Australia and New Zealand	-0-	4,000	4,000	-0-

	FY 1978			
	Unpaid 6/30/77	Grants (Adjustments)	Payments (Refunds)	Unpaid 6/30/78
Earlham College, Richmond, Ind. Periodical list for <u>Choice</u> (\$7,500-1975)	4,200	-0-	-0-	4,200
Eastern Michigan University, Ypsilanti, Mich. Project LOEX (\$41,969-1975; \$4,765-1977)	12,734	-0-	11,469	1,265
International Council on Archives, Washington, D.C. ICA Secretariat (\$72,000- 1975)	22,500	-0-	16,500	6,000
International Federation of Library Associations and Institutions, The Hague, Netherlands. Professional activities of the secretariat (\$174,000-1975)	103,014	-0-	58,000	45,014
International Office for Uni- versal Bibliographic Control (\$70,000-1974; \$144,200-1975; \$150,000-1977)	181,200	-0-	59,444	121,756
Iowa State University, Ames, Iowa. Mechanized indexing procedures applied to production of sub- ject-enhanced keyword index (\$1,926-1977)	1,176	-0-	750	426
William V. Jackson, Nashville, Tenn. Study of Latin American li- braries (\$1,445-1976)	545	(251)	294	-0-
Library of Congress, Washington, D.C. COMARC project (\$106,132-1975)	46,483	-0-	25,000	21,483
Expenses for Fourth Assembly of State Librarians at LC, May 4-6, 1977 (\$11,525-1976)	2,662	-0-	2,662	-0-

	FY 1978			
	Unpaid 6/30/77	Grants (Adjustments)	Payments (Refunds)	Unpaid 6/30/78
Integration of CONSER in national bibliographic service at LC (\$165,800-1975)	72,850	(79,859)	(7,009)	-0-
Meeting on MARC format for AACR 2	-0-	5,843	-0-	5,843
National Preservation Program, meetings of Ad Hoc Advisory Committee (\$5,960-1977)	5,675	-0-	856	4,819
Survey for microform edition of <u>Register of Additional Locations</u> (\$12,200-1975)	2,000	(2,000)	-0-	-0-
Use of the ISSN by the U.S. Postal Service	-0-	14,231	6,000	8,231
MIDLNET, Green Bay, Wis. Toward salary of a technical advisor (\$22,778-1977)	22,778	-0-	5,000	17,778
Minnesota Higher Education Coordinating Board, St. Paul, Mn. For MINITEX - Pilot test of national serials location system (\$25,000-1977)	15,000	(23,487)	(8,487)	-0-
National Association of State Universities and Land Grant Colleges, Office for Advancement of Public Negro Colleges, Atlanta, Ga. Status report on libraries of black public colleges	-0-	4,000	3,000	1,000
National Endowment for the Humanities, Washington, D.C. Continuation of College Library Program (matching grant)	-0-	60,618	60,618	-0-
The New York Public Library, New York, N.Y., on behalf of the National Citizens Emergency Committee to Save Our Public Libraries Research support (\$10,000-1977)	5,000	(45)	4,955	-0-

	FY 1978			Unpaid 6/30/78
	Unpaid 6/30/77	Grants (Adjustments)	Payments (Refunds)	
Research on future role of public libraries in preparation for White House Conference on Libraries and Information Services	-0-	15,000	-0-	15,000
OCLC, Inc., Columbus, Ohio. Study of design of a nationwide library network, of functions of individual computerized nodes in such a network, and of future governance of OCLC (\$122,000-1977)	72,000	-0-	72,000	-0-
Organization of American States, Washington, D.C. Travel report production costs of meeting to approve MARCAL (\$12,000-1976)	7,875	-0-	1,350	6,525
Pennsylvania State University, University Park, Pa. Assessment of impact of MRAP (\$31,509-1976)	3,509	(677)	2,832	-0-
William S. Pierce, Pennsylvania State University, State College, Pa. "Planning the Library Interior" (\$3,000-1975)	500	(258)	242	-0-
Princeton University, Princeton, N.J. Microform service development (\$10,000-1976)	8,750	-0-	-0-	8,750
Stockton State College, Pomona, N.J. Innovative use of <u>Books for College Libraries II</u> (\$5,150-1977)	3,150	-0-	-0-	3,150
Syracuse University, Syracuse, N.Y. Improved subject access to books by augmentation of MARC records (\$76,615-1976; \$6,958-1977)	36,615	6,958	37,000	6,573
University of California, Berkeley. National shelflist measurement project	-0-	20,000	15,000	5,000

	FY 1978			
	Unpaid 6/30/77	Grants (Adjustments)	Payments (Refunds)	Unpaid 6/30/78
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University of Chicago, Chicago, Ill. Fellowship program for holders of nonlibrary Ph.D. degrees (\$103,000-1974)	3,250	(3,490)	(240)	-0-
Network Data Management System	-0-	25,000	25,000	-0-
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University of Connecticut, Storrs, Conn. New England Academic Librarians' Writing Seminar (\$20,610-1976)	14,536	-0-	4,593	9,943
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University of North Carolina, Chapel Hill, N.C. Administration of ANSI Com- mittee Z-39 Through Dec. 1977 (\$29,649- 1976)	9,649	-0-	9,649	-0-
Through June 1978 (\$23,719- 1976)	23,719	-0-	12,500	11,219
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University of State of New York, Albany, N.Y. State Library study of state government information needs (\$25,000-1974)	4,000	(3,002)	998	-0-
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Washington University Libraries, St. Louis, Mo. To develop internal financial auditing procedures for univer- sity libraries (\$10,000-1976)	5,408	(5,388)	20	-0-
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Totals	\$1,422,323	\$636,792	\$994,388	\$916,128
	=====	(179,864)	(31,265)	=====
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